

Implementation of path following and obstacle avoidance in omnidirectional platforms

Simone Mentasti
DEIB

Politecnico di Milano
Milan, Italy

simone.mentasti@polimi.it

Giulia Fasoli
DEIB

Politecnico di Milano
Milan, Italy

giulia.fasoli@mail.polimi.it

Andrea Mauri
DEIB

Politecnico di Milano
Milan, Italy

andrea14.mauri@mail.polimi.it

Matteo Matteucci
DEIB

Politecnico di Milano
Milan, Italy

matteo.matteucci@polimi.it

Abstract—Mobile robots, in particular AGVs, have witnessed an increased interest in the last few years. This is due to the reduced costs and increased precision, which makes them highly advantageous in industrial applications like logistics. Depending on the operating scenario and constraints, this indoor robot can be built using different kinematic models (i.e., differential drive, omnidirectional, etc.). To best exploit each model’s advantage, different control and planning algorithms must be implemented. In this work, we propose a pipeline for path following and obstacle avoidance for omnidirectional robots. Our solution allows switching between different operating modes, simulating different kinematic models based on the scenario. The proposed system can achieve low error (i.e., less than 5cm) in the operating scenario.

Index Terms—Path following, obstacle avoidance, AGV, mobile robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, automation and robotics are gaining more and more importance, not only in the industrial field but also in everyday life. The main reasons behind this success are related to the higher productivity guaranteed by robots, the huge efficiency in accomplishing tasks, and finally, their possibility to operate in conditions that can be dangerous. The origin of modern robotics is strictly related to industrial applications, for example, mechanical arms, able to complete tasks quickly and with huge precision but isolated and without interactions with human operators.

This limitation is the main reason for the development of mobile robots, typically Automated guided vehicles (AGV). This solution provides a larger working environment in addition to the possibility of operating in numerous fields, for example, hospitals, hotels, warehouses, and military or agricultural applications. Moreover, mobile robots are able to operate with humans or other robots in a possibly complete autonomous and safe way, the only requirement is a reference to be followed.

In this work, we present autonomous navigation and obstacle avoidance pipeline for omnidirectional AGVs equipped with a single plane laser, shown in Fig. 1. The pipeline consists of a position controller based on a PID and an algorithm for path planning and obstacle avoidance developed especially for omnidirectional robots. As shown in Fig. 1a, the developed platform is only one component of a more extensive system designed with Oversonic Robotics [1]. Indeed, the AGVs in

(a) Robee robot from Over-sonic Robotics

(b) AGV with Mecanum wheel

(c) AGV with Omni wheel

Fig. 1: Robee humanoid robot with two omnidirectional development platform.

Fig. 1 have the task of moving the torso of the humanoid robot *robee*, allowing it to perform human-like tasks while keeping high maneuverability.

II. AUTONOMOUS NAVIGATION PIPELINE

The core component of the autonomous navigation pipeline are the obstacle avoidance and planning algorithm and the PID controller. The first one takes as inputs a static and a dynamic map of the environment, plus the position of the robot, and computes the optimal path from its position to a user-defined final goal. The PID controller instead takes the robot’s position and trajectory and computes the actuation commands to keep the robot as close as possible to the input path.

A. Obstacle avoidance and planning

Traditionally the architecture of a planning algorithm for small mobile robots is divided into two blocks, a global planner and a local planner. The first one computes the optimal trajectory from the robot position to the final goal using a preloaded map of the area. Contrarily, the second has a smaller horizon and considers dynamic obstacles, using a local dynamic map that reflects changes in the environment with respect to the original map.

For our task, we employed a state of the art A* [2] algorithm to compute the global path. The output is a discretized trajectory (i.e., a set of 2D points) from the starting position to the final goal. To exploit the omnidirectional capabilities of our AGV and provide a set of waypoints for the PID controller, we developed a custom solution for the local planner. As a first step, the algorithm computes the distance from its position to the points on the global path, and if it can find one under a fixed threshold, the point is set as the next waypoint. Otherwise, a reinitialization of the global planner is triggered. To take into account dynamic obstacles, which do not appear in the map used to compute the global plan, we implemented a vector field histogram (VFH) algorithm using the data from the local map. Given a goal from the local planner, we consider a circumference of radius equal to the distance to the subgoal centered in the robot position. This circle is defined as an array with 360 elements corresponding to 360 points in the 2D plan separated by 1 degree, where the first is the goal. Then, using Bresenham’s algorithm [3] we compute the lines on the discretized map that connect the position to each point of the circle. Next, starting from the goal position, we check if the line intersects an obstacle. If the trajectory is free, it is sent to the PID controller. Instead, if it is partially occupied, we look for the closest left and right points on the circle and perform iteratively the same check until a free path is found or the whole list of points is analyzed.

B. PID control

The output of the PID controller in time domain is the following one:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t u(\tau) d(\tau) + K_d \frac{de}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where $e(t)$ is the tracking error between the set-point and the measured output, while K_p , K_i , K_d are respectively the proportional, integral, and derivative gain, which are the parameters to be tuned. A known problem of the integral component of PID is the phenomenon called windup. If the initial set-point change is so high that the actuator saturates, the integral term continuously increases, reaching its maximum value when the error is zero. From this point on, the output can not leave the saturation condition until the error remains negative for a sufficiently long time allowing the integral term to decrease. This can generate a huge overshoot and a dump oscillation. To avoid this issue, we decided to adopt the back-calculation method as presented in [4]. In this case, when the output saturates, K_i is recomputed in order to give a value at the saturation limit, the integrator is reset with a time period T_t , a good rule of thumb consists in setting $T_t = \sqrt{T_i \cdot T_d}$ where $T_i = \frac{K_p}{K_i}$ and $T_d = \frac{K_d}{K_p}$ are respectively the integrator and the derivative time constants. Since the robot moves on a 2D plane, the control is performed by three independent PIDs, two for the position and one for the orientation. Since the robot can freely rotate and move in each direction, the PIDs are completely independent.

Fig. 2: trajectory of the development robot performing obstacle avoidance. In red the computed global plan, in green the real-time computed subgoals and in blue the performed trajectory.

Finally, we implemented the possibility of switching between two navigation modes to allow greater modularity during navigation for different possible applications and leverage the advantages of an omnidirectional platform. With the first one, the AGV behaves as a classical omnidirectional robot, while with the second, the robot drives similarly to differential drive ones. In the second case, when a waypoint is generated, we evaluate the direction between the actual position of the robot and the x and y position of the set-point. During the motion, we close the loop around the ankle evaluated in this way, removing the independency between the three PIDs so that the robots can move only forward. When they reach a certain distance from the set-point, the desired angle becomes the orientation of the waypoint, and the three loops are again independent. Contrary, for the first scenario, all control-loop are constantly evaluated independently.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To validate the whole navigation pipeline, the robot has been tasked to perform different paths, like traversing narrow areas and avoiding obstacles. Fig. 2 shows the results of a simple obstacle avoidance task. It is possible to appreciate how the effective trajectory of the robot is extremely close to the computed path, with a mean distance error lower than $4cm$ and a maximum error lower than $6cm$. Moreover, the robot effectively plans a curved trajectory around the obstacle, taking the shortest path but, at the same time, avoiding the collision.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a pipeline for path planning and obstacle avoidance for omnidirectional robots. The experimental validation performed on real robots has achieved good results, with acceptable error for autonomous navigation, deeming it acceptable to be used in an operating scenario as part of the Oversonic Robee platform.

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